

A Data-Driven Framework on Topology Optimization for Soft-Rigid Grippers

Valerio Bo, Enrico Turco, Maria Pozzi, Monica Malvezzi, and Domenico Prattichizzo

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy

University of Siena, Siena, Italy

valerio.bo@iit.it, enrico.turco@iit.it, maria.pozzi@unisi.it, monica.malvezzi@unisi.it, dprattichizzo@unisi.it

Abstract—In this abstract, we propose a data-driven approach to enhance robotic gripper design using topology optimization. Our methodology involves three sequential phases. First, we acquired from the gripper component force signals sensed during grasping simulations, and after, we analyzed them using pixel connectivity and Dynamic Time Warping algorithms in the second phase. These analyses provide instructions for topology optimization performed in the third phase. Testing the method in simulation on a soft-rigid gripper, we found that our proposed architecture both optimizes material usage and improves the grasp success rate compared to the original gripper design.

Index Terms—Grasping, Grippers, Soft Robot Design

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, optimal design methods have been exploited in robotic manipulation to create grippers capable of handling diverse objects and executing specific in-hand manipulation actions. Topology Optimization is a prominent technique in this context, aiming to maximize performance while minimizing material usage [1].

Traditional topology optimization algorithms consider contacts between grippers and objects using pressure loading or predefined constraints based on the designer’s intuition about probable grasp points. However, this approach may be suitable for simple grippers, but it might not be realistic for more complex robots. Conversely, simulation data can provide helpful information for the design of robotic grippers [2].

In this abstract, we propose a novel approach for topologically optimizing the design of the Soft ScoopGripper, a tendon-driven soft gripper with an embedded rigid part [3], using contact force data from dynamic grasp simulations [4]. Our pipeline (shown in Figure 1) involves different phases where force signals from grasping simulations are recorded and processed. The analyzed signal information is then translated into loadings and constraints for topology optimization.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The framework proposed in this work allows to topologically optimize parts of a gripper based on accurate a priori information on its grasping capabilities. The framework comprises three main phases, as illustrated in Figure 1. In the first phase, dynamic simulations of multiple grasps are performed using the chosen gripper. The gripper component’s

Fig. 1: Schematic of the proposed framework.

surface is divided into a grid, with the grid size defined as a user parameter. Each grid element contains a simulated force/torque sensor to characterize hand-object interactions during grasping. We then placed several objects with an initial object orientation set to a value equal to $\kappa\pi/6$ radians, with $\kappa=1, \dots, 12$. Using a force sensor placed on the surface where the objects lay, we considered a grasp successful if no force was detected within 3 seconds after completing the grasp execution. We gathered data from 600 simulated grasps.

In the second phase, we processed the recorded force signals to obtain a set of instructions for the topology optimization. First, we separated the successful grasps from the failed ones. After that we created a 2D image in which each color indicates a different magnitude of the force. To get a higher resolution, we up-sampled the data using Gridded Interpolation. An example of final 2D image grid is shown in Fig. 2a. We then obtained a binary image using a threshold value for the force magnitude. We determined the threshold to distinguish an object contact from a finger one. To make the information more homogeneous we used a pixel-connectivity algorithm to create uniform blobs of pixels (see Fig. 2b). Each blob is described through a limited set of parameters, including its center, its area, etc. For each image we just kept the largest blob, thus selecting only the area in which most of the hand-object interactions arise, as shown in Fig. 2c.

After having obtained the blob, we used the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm to measure the similarity between the different grasping trials in terms of evolution of the parameters of the blobs. This information was then used to cluster grasping trials in which the blobs evolved in similar

This work was supported by Progetto Prin 2017 “TIGHT: Tactile Intelligence for Humans and Artificial systems”, prot. 2017SB48FP.

Fig. 2: Analysis of a single time instant of a single grasping trial: (a) 2D grid of the recorded forces, (b) image of the blobs obtained from the pixel-connectivity algorithm, and (c) image of the blob with the largest area.

ways. We adopted the K-medoid clustering algorithm and the Calinski-Harabasz Criterion or Variance Ratio Criterion (VRC) to determine the optimal number of clusters k .

In the third and final phase, we translated the force signal distributions into the information necessary to perform a classic topology optimization of the examined piece. We conducted the topology study with the density method. We specified the loads necessary to actuate the component and its fixed boundary linking the part to the rest of the gripper. Therefore, we applied the results evaluated in the data processing as boundary loads. The final output consists of the STereoLithography (STL) file of the optimized component.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

After acquiring the STL file of the optimized scoop, we conducted an analysis to demonstrate its effectiveness and utility. The purpose of the test was to validate the success rate and force distributions of the newly designed scoop in comparison to the original one. We performed 300 grasp simulations per scoop and included 7 objects that were part of the previous analysis, as well as 3 new objects to demonstrate the generalizability of our approach.

The evaluation of the experiments focused on two aspects: the grasp success rate and the intensity of forces applied on the scoop. Concerning the first aspect, we achieved 189 successful grasps out of 300 attempts for the original scoop and 232 successful grasps out of 300 attempts for the optimized scoop. The grasp success rates for each object are provided in Table I. As for the second aspect, we assessed the force signals recorded on the surface of both the original and optimized scoops, as mentioned in the earlier analysis.

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the results obtained during the testing phase, we can confidently assert that the proposed framework significantly enhances the gripper performance. Overall, the grasping success rate increases when utilizing the optimized component.

In particular, the newly designed component demonstrates superior effectiveness when handling objects that were previously challenging for the original scoop. Notable examples include the metal mug, the banana, and the screwdriver, with a combined total of 68 successful grasps out of 90 attempts,

TABLE I: Success rates of the testing phase for both the original and optimal designed scoops.

Objects	Obj. ID	Original Scoop	Optimal Scoop
Triangular Toy	1	24/30	25/30
Bridge Toy	2	19/30	18/30
Metal Mug	3	14/30	27/30
Sugar Box	4	23/30	23/30
Cracker Box	5	23/30	25/30
Tuna Can	6	18/30	20/30
Apple	7	26/30	30/30
Banana	8	10/30	20/30
Mustard	9	20/30	25/30
Screwdriver	10	12/30	21/30
	Total	189/300	232/300

compared to only 36 successful grasps with the original scoop. The reason behind this improvement lies in the fact that the original scoop's flat surface allowed the objects to roll outside the gripper's boundaries. By introducing constraints and creating a concavity in the center of the scoop during the design phase, we were able to counteract the rolling effect.

Moreover, the analysis of the sensed forces corroborates our previous observations. The forces along the x -axis are now more concentrated at the scoop's center, while the forces along the y -axis show a desirable trend, as the objects are effectively moved toward the palm of the gripper during the grasping process. This further supports the efficacy of the optimized component in improving grasp stability and performance.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, we present a framework to enhance gripper topology optimization using data analysis from previous grasping simulations. We tested our method on the Soft Scoop-Gripper and observed that the proposed framework improves the component and prevents unwanted gripper behaviors.

In future works, we aim to enhance the framework by incorporating additional mechanical analyses and exploring composite optimizations for different components. Another potential improvement is to develop a closed-loop version of this work, where components are optimized and updated after a certain number of iterations. Furthermore, we plan to investigate the transition of this method from simulated to real robotic grippers, evaluating the feasibility of acquiring training data through specialized sensors.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. P. Bendsoe and O. Sigmund, *Topology optimization: theory, methods, and applications*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2003.
- [2] V. Bo, E. Turco, M. Pozzi, M. Malvezzi, and D. Prattichizzo, "Automated design of embedded constraints for soft hands enabling new grasp strategies," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 11 346–11 353, 2022.
- [3] G. Salvietti, Z. Iqbal, M. Malvezzi, T. Eslami, and D. Prattichizzo, "Soft hands with embodied constraints: The soft scoopgrasper," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Robotics and Automation*, Montreal, Canada, May 2019, pp. 2758–2764.
- [4] V. Bo, E. Turco, M. Pozzi, M. Malvezzi, and D. Prattichizzo, "A data-driven topology optimization framework for designing robotic grippers," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.